

UDC 620

ANALYSIS OF METHODS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF SOLAR COLLECTORS USED FOR HOT WATER SUPPLY

SAMIRA AKBAROVA MISIRKHAN

PhD in technical sciences, associate prof., Azerbaijan University Architecture and Construction, Baku, Azerbaijan

ZARINTAJ RANJIBARI-AMOUDIZAJ AKHMAD

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction
Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract: *The purpose of this work is to develop the fundamentals of a methodology for evaluating the efficiency of solar thermal systems. **Research Methodology:** The study is based on general scientific methodology, which implies a systematic approach to problem-solving. **Results:** The article presents a methodology for assessing the efficiency of solar thermal systems used for heating and hot water supply in residential, agricultural, and industrial buildings and facilities. These systems are primarily used in regions with favorable climatic conditions. Azerbaijan is one of the most suitable countries for solar energy utilization. The amount of solar energy incident on a horizontal surface throughout the year varies approximately from 1500 to 2000 kWh per m². The annual duration of solar radiation ranges from 2000 to 3000 hours. This value is high compared to other countries due to the country's geographical location, the number of sunny hours, and other natural conditions, indicating broad potential for solar energy use. Solar thermal systems are competitive and can provide positive economic, social, and environmental effects. **Application Area:** Design and implementation of solar energy systems, systems combined with solar collectors, heat pumps, and thermal accumulators, as well as simple water heating devices intended for supplying hot water and heating for residential houses and other consumers requiring low-temperature heat. The development of these technologies is crucial for the gradual transition to houses fully supplied with solar thermal energy. **Conclusion:** Precise calculations and tests conducted in Azerbaijan show that these solar systems have high energy and economic efficiency.*

Keywords: *Solar thermal system, renewable energy sources, heat collectors, energy efficiency, methodology.*

The use of renewable energy sources is becoming increasingly relevant, as traditional energy sources are limited and their use harms the environment. Consequently, the role of solar energy in obtaining environmentally friendly heat and electricity is growing.

Solar thermal systems, photovoltaic panels, wind energy technologies, and systems combined with heat pumps are considered promising energy systems, allowing significant savings on conventional fuel. For cost-effective heating of residential buildings, as well as for highly efficient heating systems with zero energy consumption from electricity and gas networks, it is recommended to use solar thermal systems that include heat pumps, heat collectors, and solar photovoltaic converters [1].

The efficiency of energy systems, particularly solar systems, comprises two main components: technical (energy) efficiency and economic efficiency. The energy efficiency of solar thermal systems primarily depends on the technical characteristics of the collectors (the design and efficiency of the absorbing element, the type of its coating — which can be selective or simply matte black paint; the thermal insulation properties of the collector body; the material and optical properties of the transparent cover). Therefore, it is impossible to assess the energy efficiency of solar systems or make conclusions about it without first studying the technical characteristics of the designed solar collectors [2, 5].

Main Section: The primary goal in the design and implementation of solar energy systems is to minimize the cost of the produced heat or electricity. In some cases, a system with lower energy efficiency (lower coefficient of performance) but requiring less financial investment may, in fact, be more cost-effective. Therefore, in any case, the expected thermal-technical characteristics of the collectors must first be determined, and only then should the economic efficiency be calculated based on them.

The total heat loss coefficient of a collector is denoted as U_L . The heat loss coefficient takes into account all heat losses of the collector, including losses through the top transparent cover, the base, and the walls.

The next parameter, $(\tau * \alpha)$, represents the relative absorption capacity of the collector (it is the product of the transmittance coefficient of the collector's transparent cover and the absorptance of the black coating on the absorbing surface). This coefficient is the main optical characteristic of the collector.

The total heat loss coefficient of the collector is considered the main parameter that determines its thermal-technical characteristics.

To determine the product of the total heat loss coefficient and the efficiency coefficient of the absorbing panel ($F^1 * U_L$), tests are conducted on a thermal-hydraulic stand installed in laboratory conditions. The collector is mounted on a special support at a 45° angle to the horizontal and connected to the stand's piping system. The circulation system of the stand is filled with water, ensuring that no air remains in the circuit. The thermostat pump is turned on, and the water flow through the collector is adjusted to 15 kg/(m²·h) using a flow meter.

The condition for performing the tests is that the water flow does not vary by more than ±1% during the test. The test is considered to be in a steady state if the temperature of the water at the collector inlet and outlet, as well as the ambient air temperature, does not change by more than 0.1°C within 10 minutes. During the tests (20 minutes after reaching steady state), the water temperature at the collector inlet and outlet, ambient air temperature, and water flow through the collector are recorded.

The tests are carried out with water flow rates in the range of 15–25 kg/(m²·h) and at collector inlet water temperatures of 30, 40, 50, and 60°C. The temperature is changed for each test. Thus, at least four tests are conducted.

Based on the results of the tests, the product of the collector's total heat loss coefficient and the efficiency coefficient of the absorbing panel is determined using the following formula (1) [6]:

$$U^L = \frac{G * C_p * (T_{inlet} - T_{outlet})}{A * (T_j^c - T_{air})} \quad (1)$$

Here:

U^L – total heat loss coefficient, W/(m²·°C);

G – water flow through the collector, kg/h;

A – area of the heat-absorbing surface, m²;

C_p – specific heat capacity of water, W·h/(kg·°C);

T_{inlet} – temperature of water entering the collector, °C;

T_{outlet} – temperature of water leaving the collector, °C;

T_{air} – ambient air temperature, °C;

T_j^c – average temperature of the water inside the collector, equal to the arithmetic mean of the inlet and outlet water temperatures, i.e., $T_j^c = \frac{T_{inlet} + T_{outlet}}{2}$.

Another important parameter of a solar collector is its efficiency coefficient (η), which measures its thermal effectiveness. The efficiency coefficient is calculated as the ratio of the thermal energy obtained over a certain period, Q_p , to the solar energy incident on the collector surface during the same period, J [4].

In the second phase of the study, tests are conducted considering the interaction of all components of the solar thermal system, including the determination of the daily, monthly, and

annual useful output of the system under varying temperatures and actinometric conditions. The operation of the solar system is described by the energy balance equation, which divides the solar radiation energy into useful energy and losses. The overall energy balance of the system can be expressed using the following formula (2) [2]:

$$A_c [J * R(\tau * \alpha)]_s = Q_p + Q_T + Q_a \quad (2)$$

Here:

A_c – Area of the collector;

J – Density of the total solar radiation flux incident on a unit area of the collector surface;

R – The ratio of the flux density, converted to any plane, to the flux density on the plane of the collector orientation;

$(\tau * \alpha)$ – The effective absorptance of the collector relative to the total (direct and diffuse) solar radiation;

Q_p – Heat flux transferred to the user through the heating and hot water supply system;

Q_T – Heat loss from collectors, pipes, and the thermal accumulator to the environment through radiation and convection;

Q_a – Heat flux stored in the system's thermal accumulator.

It should be noted that the thermal energy stored in the accumulator can later be considered useful; therefore, it is more convenient to determine the actual heat output of the system (Q_p) over a time interval Δt using formula (3):

$$Q_p = G * C_p (T_{outlet} - T_{inlet}) * \Delta t \quad (3)$$

Here:

G – Flow rate of the heat carrier exiting the collectors, kg/h;

C_p – Specific heat capacity of the heat carrier, W·h/(kg·°C);

T_{inlet} and T_{outlet} – Temperatures of the heat carrier at the collector inlet and outlet;

Δt – Duration of the time interval between measurements, hours.

To more accurately determine the useful heat entering the heating and hot water supply system—taking into account all heat losses from the pipes, accumulator, and collectors—the temperature of the heat carrier should be measured on the user side of the accumulator, i.e., at the outlet and inlet, not on the collector side. Formula (3) is used for the calculation. The result of the calculation will be negative, indicating that in this case, heat is being released from the accumulator, i.e., the accumulator is cooling.

According to this methodology, the test results automatically take into account the two main technical parameters of the solar collectors: the total heat loss coefficient and the effective absorptance. In this case, there is no need for preliminary testing of the collectors to determine the parameters mentioned above. If measurements are taken hourly, the results of the calculations indicate the total hourly output of the collectors or the system.

To measure the intensity of the solar radiation flux, an M-80 pyranometer is used together with a GSA galvanometer. The M-80 pyranometer allows determination of the total (direct + diffuse) solar radiation flux intensity. The pyranometer is installed on the plane of the collector's absorbing surface.

An anemometer is used to measure wind speed. During system testing, the anemometer is placed 3 meters away at the height of the collectors upper edge.

To measure the liquid flow through the collectors, a high-precision laboratory flow meter is used, which is installed at the collector inlet.

Chromel-alumel thermocouples are used to measure temperature parameters. The thermocouples are installed at the collector inlet and outlet. For calibration of the thermocouples, laboratory mercury thermometers with a scale division of 0.2°C are used.

The daily output is determined as the sum of the hourly output values.

The daily output of the system, Q_{daily} , is determined using the following formula (4):

$$Q_{daily} = G * C_p (T_{outlet} - T_{inlet})^{\Sigma} \quad (4)$$

Here:

G and C_p – Flow rate and specific heat capacity of the heat carrier passing through the heater (absorber);

$T_{outlet} - T_{inlet}$ – The sum of the temperature differences of the heat carrier at the heater inlet and outlet, measured at equal time intervals (1 hour) throughout the day.

In the operating mode of the solar system with a constant heat-carrier flow, the quantity ($T_{outlet} - T_{inlet}$) varies over time due to fluctuations in solar radiation, ambient air temperature, wind speed, and other factors. Therefore, $(T_{outlet} - T_{inlet})^2$ is determined as the sum of the temperature differences from a series of measurements taken at different times during the test period.

The simplified calculation of the system’s monthly output can be performed using the following formula (5):

$$Q_{month} = Q_{daily} * (n_{sunny} + \frac{1}{2}n_{partly\ sunny}) \quad (5)$$

Here, n_{sunny} and $n_{partly\ sunny}$ are the numbers of sunny and ‘partly sunny’ days in the month. Two partly sunny days are considered equivalent to one “conventional sunny day.” To determine the actual output of the solar thermal system over a longer period - such as several months or a year - heat-measuring devices installed at the point where heat is extracted from the solar system are used. These devices monitor and record the hot water flow and the temperature difference at the inlet and outlet of the solar system.

Results. According to the methodology described above, the economic efficiency of a solar thermal system designed for a family of three, intended for hot water supply and partial house heating, has been calculated. The calculated heat load of the house is 10 kW, of which 1.4 kW is allocated for hot water supply. The annual heat consumption is as follows: for heating – 17,000 kWh/year; for hot water supply – 3,500 kWh/year. The total annual heat demand of the house is 20,500 kWh/year. The total surface area of the solar collectors is 10 m².

The experimental solar system, equipped with polycarbonate collectors, was installed at an experimental site at a 45° angle. During the collector tests, the wind speed did not exceed 5 m/s on clear sunny days. The tests were carried out with a constant water flow through the collectors of 15 kg/(m²·h). Table 1 presents the results of the daily tests of the solar system conducted in mid-August. The daily test results for other months of the year are shown in Table 2. The tests were conducted over at least 3–5 sunny days each month.

As seen from Table 1, the daily heat output of the solar system with a collector area of 10 m² reaches 46 kWh/day on a sunny day in August. The total solar energy incident on the collector surface is 64.64 kWh/day (radiation intensity per 1 m² is 6.464 kWh/day).

Table 1 – Test results of the solar water heating system on a clear sunny day in August under the climatic conditions of Baku city.

Time of day Parameter	7 ⁰⁰	8 ⁰⁰	9 ⁰⁰	10 ⁰⁰	11 ⁰⁰	12 ⁰⁰	13 ⁰⁰	14 ⁰⁰	15 ⁰⁰	16 ⁰⁰	17 ⁰⁰	During the day
J W/m ²	160	370	585	760	880	920	886	766	592	377	168	6464
T _{am. air} , °C	23	23	24	25	26	27	29	30	30	29	28	
V, m/s	2,0	2,0	1,5	1,5	1,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	
T _{inlet} , °C	30	30	32	35	36	36	37	38	38	37	36	
T _{outlet} , °C	35	45	57	64	70	73	73	67	60	50	41	
Y _{sys} , W/m ²	115	270	430	540	620	660	650	550	430	270	120	
Q _{heat} , W*hour	1150	2700	4300	5400	6200	6600	6500	5500	4300	2700	1200	46550

J - Total solar radiation intensity on the collector surface, W/m²;
 T_{am.air}, T_{inlet} ∨ T_{outlet} - Ambient air temperature, and temperatures at the collector inlet and outlet, respectively;
 V - Wind speed, m/s;
 Y_{system} - Heat flux per unit area of the system, W/m²;
 Q_{heat} - Heat output of the system, W·h.

Energy efficiency (or the useful work coefficient – η) is defined as the ratio Q_{heat} / J. In our case, the efficiency of the collectors is 46,550 / 64,640 = 0.72. This value is on par with the best foreign counterparts and indicates that the polycarbonate solar collectors manufactured in Baku meet world standards in terms of thermal performance.

Table 2 – Monthly heat output of the solar system with a collector area of 10 m² under the climatic conditions of Baku city.

Months	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Year
n	4	4	16	15	17	20	22	25	23	20	14	5	
Q _{day} , kWh	2,5	3,0	3,5	4,4	4,6	5,0	4,9	4,8	4,7	4,5	4,0	3,0	
Q _{month} kWh	100	120	560	660	782	1000	1080	1220	1078	890	560	150	8190

n – total number of sunny and “conventional sunny” days in the month;
 Q_{day} – System output on a clear sunny day, kWh;
 Q_{month} – Monthly output, kWh.

The potential monthly output of the solar system is calculated taking into account the number of sunny and partly sunny days. The annual heat output of the solar system is determined as the sum of the monthly outputs and equals 8,190 kWh.

Here, a small assumption is made that all energy produced by the solar system is used efficiently, i.e., directed to house heating and hot water supply. The goal is to design the house’s heating system so that the heat and temperature potential of the solar system is utilized first, and only when the solar system’s capacity is exhausted does an additional gas-or electric-powered heat source operate.

In our example, the solar energy replacement coefficient is 8,190 / 20,500 = 0.4, meaning that 40% of the total heat load of the house is supplied by the solar thermal system.

Conclusions. The test results of the experimental batch of polycarbonate solar collectors demonstrated their sufficiently high energy and economic efficiency as well as resistance to atmospheric effects, which allows us to recommend their use as the basis for solar thermal systems for mass application in the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Solar thermal systems can be used for heating and hot water supply in any residential, agricultural, or industrial buildings located in regions with favorable climatic conditions, i.e., areas with a relatively high number of sunny days per year. They can also be applied for heating water in pools, providing hot water for individual or collective consumers, and heating buildings.

From an energy and economic perspective, for residential solar water heaters, it is advisable to use low-cost collectors with good thermal and optical parameters, single-layer transparent covers, and without selective coating, because the use of double-layer transparent covers and selective coatings on the absorber surface significantly increases the collector cost without proportionally improving its energy efficiency.

REFERENCES:

1. Alkhasov A. B., Renewable energy. M.: FIZMATLIT, 2010. 256 p.
2. Amadziev A. M., Dibirov M. G., Dibirova M. M., Gurulev D. S. New materials for solar collectors // Food industry. No. 2. 2008.
3. Anderson B. Solar energy, the basics of building design. Moscow: «Stroyizdat», 1982.
4. Daffy D. A., Beckman U. A. Thermal processes using solar energy. Moscow: MIR publishing House, 1977.
5. Dibirov M. G., Amadiou A. M., Gurulev D. S., Dibirova, G. M. «Polycarbonate solar collector – 1». Patent for utility model. No. 84093.
6. Dibirov M. G., Amadiou M. A., Dibirova M. M. Report R & d «Development of polycarbonate solar collectors» // Vntic. Reg. № 01200952464.
7. Magomedova N. Ah. The concept of development of renewable energy of the Republic of Dagestan as an integral part of innovative economic policy // Regional economy: theory and practice. 2010. No. 38.
8. Popel O. S., Frid S. E. On the use of solar water heaters in the climatic conditions of Central Russia. // En-ergy Saving Problems. No. 7. 2001.
9. Sibikin Y. D. alternative and renewable energy sources: textbook/ 2nd edition. M.: KNORUS, 2012. 240 p.
10. Fortov B. E., Popel O. C. Energy in the modern world. Dolgoprudny: Publishing House. house «Intellect», 2011. 167 p.
11. The impact of wind Power in Ireland on the operation of traditional power plants and economic consequences. ESB National Grid, 2004.
12. Dahmann J. and K. Baldwin. Understanding the current state of U. S. defense systems and implications for system design // IEEE Systems Conference. Montreal, 2008.
13. Pyster P. Gardner. Critical success factors in systems engineering // Tactical systems division, 2006.